

**Literature review of: States and Social Policies by
Theda Skocpol and Edwin Amenta
(1986)**

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Literature Review

States and Social Policies by Skocpol and Amenta (1986) is an Annual Review that aims to describe the determinants of Social Policies, as well its arguments connected with the Welfare States and its relevant authors throughout the time.

Firstly, basic concepts are needed to understand the context. Per definition, States are organizations that extract resources and attempt to extend coercive control and political authority over territories and the people within them. Policies are actions pursued through states with the goal of defending their territories and revenues, through military and economic policies, that are results of productivity and trading. Therefore, it also directly affects the life conditions of the individuals, as it can determine mass education, access to health care, working conditions, environmental influences, etc.

Between the 1880s and 1920s, during the process of industrial growth, social insurance and pension programs were launched in Europe, the Americas, and Australia, aiming to buffer workers in market economies against income losses due to disability, old age, ill health, unemployment, or loss of a family. By the time of World War II, most of the leading industrial-capitalist democracies became self-proclaimed "welfare states", and had used the programs in one way or another.

Furthermore, the first determinant that is addressed is the logic of industrialism and economic growth, in which, regardless of the form of regime or political influences, nations moved from traditional-agrarian to modern-industrial. Because of industrialism, new resources become available to invest in technology and basic social needs, as an aging population would decrease economic development. Once the research became more closely examined, this perspective was undermined.

Besides that, capitalism was also analyzed as a possible determinant. Neo-Marxists thought "social reproduction" comes with needs to prepare skilled wageworkers, as well allow their families to consume goods and services. So, in order to preserve the growing labor, the authorities had to deal with the possible discontent from the fate of the injured, sick, elderly people and many more. However, these theorists failed to explain and identify the main political actors in the role of shaping policies.

Other pundits mentioned the influence of democratic structures in social policies. Myles (1984) finds that competitive elections between 1945 and 1974 "Faced with a high level of competition at the polls, it would appear that parties do indeed bid up the quality of pension entitlements in the pursuit of votes". Tufte also added that pre-election benefit increases and post-election tax increases, suggesting an "electoral-economic cycle". Nonetheless, Frey & Schneider (1978, 1982) slightly modify Tufte's argument by arguing that governments must be in a "popularity deficit" before they will manipulate social policies prior to elections, otherwise governing parties will act on their established ideological principles.

In addition, the effects of popular protest were analyzed by Frances Piven and Richard Cloward and showed that new or increased welfare benefits have occurred as concessions by elites to protests by the poor and workers, only when economic and political crises render elites in a formal democracy unable simply to repress "disruptive" demonstrations. That resulted in a slight impact on welfare outlays, not being in line with the demands posed, and once popular disruptions cease, some benefits may be retracted.

The social democratic model proposes that the earlier and more fully the workers become organized into centralized unions and parties, the earlier and more "completely" a welfare state develops. A study examines Sweden, a social democratic prototype, which has a very high proportion of its labor force organized into centralized unions. Yet for all the favorable evidence, the pure social democratic model has not been established beyond question as a sufficient guide to when, how, and why industrialized capitalist democracies create and expand social policies.

Among the alternatives, party systems and organizations were also an object of the research, and were one of the last arguments to try to prove that politics really matter for the development of social policies in capitalist democracies. Wilensky (1981) perceived that Catholic party power from 1919 to 1976 positively affected social security, in large part

because it was associated with corporatism bargaining and invisible taxes. Castles (1981) argues that "education is related to right-wing strength, health spending to social democratic strength and class politics, and public income maintenance seems unaffected by political considerations". As well, right-wing and center parties are least antagonistic to social transfer payments, because these interfere very little with the operations of the market. Moreover, Amenta (1984) found that in the US, the more patronage-oriented and factionalized a state's Democratic Party is, the longer it took to pass unemployment insurance in the 1930s.

Scholars argued that social policies must be analyzed in an international manner. Cameron (1978) found that "openness to the international economy" was even a better predictor than social democratic power (which is said to be enhanced by openness). Because of the constant adjustment to shifts in the global market, "governments in small open economies have tended to provide a variety of income supplements in the form of social security schemes, health insurance, unemployment benefits, employment subsidies and even job training". Katzenstein (1985) fleshes out this thesis, demonstrating that seven small trade-dependent European democracies use "democratic corporatism" bargains among unions, business, and government to coordinate economic and social policies.

Meanwhile, for Latin American nations, the development of social policies has largely ignored international trade as such and even has suggested instead of the market, it is instituted as parts of state strategies to promote the economic development of nations situated in dependent positions in the capitalist system. For example, Spalding (1980) links the launching of Mexican social security in the 1940s to the state's industrialization strategy, in which new social security taxes were to be used to help finance state investments, and key groups of workers had to be politically managed. So social policies could be effectively used for the bureaucratic cooptation and control of strategic sectors, as highlighted in Malloy's (1979) work.

For the first time, it has been suggested that states have instituted social policies as part of their own organizational and territorial consolidation. Tilly (1975) observes, while comparing England, France, Spain, and Brandenburg-Prussia, how the efforts of early modern European "state makers" to extract revenues and build armies became intertwined with policies created to stimulate the production of food and regulate its availability to potentially rebellious peasants.

Similarly, comparing nations in the nineteenth-century in the same region, Ramirez & Boli (1985) argue that mass schooling was instituted at moments of crisis, as part of efforts by authorities to improve the competitive potential of their nations in the international system. According to a number of writers (Andreski 1968; Janowitz 1976: Ch.3; and Titmuss 1958), mass citizen mobilization for modern warfare has encouraged more generous and universalist public social provision, especially when the line between soldiers and civilians

becomes blurred, as it did in World War II. Therefore, democratic politicians appealing for popular support in wartime can be seen as the agents of this linkage, although systematic cross-national evidence is still lacking. Wilensky (1975) explored whether social policies, once established, may be fiscally stunted by the need to compete with military establishments. He then finds support for his view that military spending from 1950 to 1952 retarded, but did not halt, increases in national social spending. During 1939 to 1968, Russett (1970) found significant trade-offs between military spending and spends for education and health. However, Russett (1982) found no significant military versus social spending trade-offs for the periods 1947-1979.

Afterwards, international cultural modeling was also a topic of determination. According to John Meyer, the "cultural school" of world system analysis and the spread of a competitive state system from Europe to the entire globe has been accompanied and facilitated by the shared features thought to be necessary for any "modern nation-state". Despite world-economic situations or domestic characteristics, similar forms of social policies were found in organizations such as the United Nations or the International Labor Organization. Even so, some nations tend to avoid rather than initiate international models, as the US found the European social insurance policies were positive models before World War I, but became negative models afterwards. Highly aggregated quantitative studies are unlikely to be sufficient to pin down the processes needed from across time periods of world history, and to allow for negative as well as positive international modeling.

In this degree, the impact of states on social policymaking are starting to be reconceptualized as key actors and as consequential structures and sets of policies. Flora & Alber (1981) found the executive leaders of the states are thought to be the ones most likely to initiate new social policies, as in the interest in using it to facilitate economic development whilst deflecting popular discontent. It can even be a mode of intervention states use to cope with problems, ranging from direct state ownership or provision of services, through public expenditures, to the use of taxes to modify the actions of determined populations groups. Yet, Hage & Hanneman (1980) argue that in some regions, centralized states can either promote or retard social expenditures.

Once social policies are implemented, they reshape politics as they change the public agendas and the patterns of group conflict, which is labeled as "Policy feedbacks". Wilensky maintains that "visible taxes" arouse generalized public resistance to welfare state expansion, whereas democratic politicians who use "invisible taxes" can "yet stay cool". These ideas resemble the theory of economists who discuss the fiscal illusion, referring to characteristics built into tax systems that lead voters to underestimate the cost of public goods.

There are, however, many disagreements over how to classify various kinds of taxes. While Wilensky views policy as feedbacks, Hecló (1974a) thinks of 'political learning', seeing politics primarily as a process by which people in power "puzzle", as he quoted, about solutions to societal problems. It also reacts to the previous policies and asks how the government means at hand can be used to do better with adjusted or alternative policies. Hence, Esping-Andersen seeks to explain why the Danish Social Democratic Party and welfare state are losing support, while their Swedish counterparts are proving more resilient in the face of fiscal stringencies. He determines a detailed analysis of the political effects of major policies instituted in each country. Therefore, concluding that the policy choices made by parties in power are crucial and can directly affect various social groups, the policies thus either undermine or to extend the electorate.

In conclusion, Skocpol and Amenta (1986) review provides an extensive analysis of the multiple determinants shaping social policy development across nations and time periods. The authors emphasize the complex correlation of industrialization, capitalism, democracy, party structures, globalization and the institutional capacities of states. Ultimately, arguing that the understanding of welfare states requires a multidimensional approach, that recognizes the central role of the state as an active agent in shaping social outcomes.

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